

WORK CULTURE AND HRD CLIMATE AT CADBURY INDIA LTD

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ABSTRACT

Work culture plays an important role in extracting the best out of employees and making them stick to the organization for a longer duration. An organization's success is determined by skills and competence of its employees. Hence sound HRD climate is essential to develop skills and competence in the employee. A congenial Human of the goal of the business organization. HRD climate consist work culture surrounded in the organization. It is also necessary to facilitate HRD activities. Cadbury India ltd. is a big player in the present detergent market. It offers quality products ranging from cosmetics, soap, detergent powder etc. Present study describes views regarding work culture and HRD Climate at Cadbury India Ltd. Total 50 employees has been selected from the administrative department to find out HRD climate. Four parameters have been considered i.e. Prospect, work culture, professionalism and Training & development to explore respondent's view about HRD climate. Single factor ANOVA has been performed using Excel Sheet to find out variances among four parameters. Findings of the study indicate that there are significant variances among all four parameters considered to explore Work culture and HRD climate.

INTRODUCTION:

Organisation is considered to be complete organisation after including top authority to bottom line of workers. And whenever we talk about development at organisational level effort is needed from top level to bottom level. Top authority should not have thinking in their mind that their task is to only take decisions but they should also emphasized on proper implementation of decision by adopting various controlling technique. Bottom level workers should have loyal mind-set towards their organisation. Bottom level workers have to work with dedication. They should have realisation that organisation is their organisation. To prepare Human Resource Development Climate, Manager and Supervisor's responsibilities are more or we can say that they are the key players. Manager and Supervisors have to help the employees to develop the competencies in the employees. To help the employees at lower level they need to updated properly and they need to share their expertise and experience with employees.

Faith upon Employee's:

In the process of developing HRD Climate employer should have faith on its employee's capabilities. Means whatever amount is invested that should be based on development of employees. Top management should trust the employees that after making huge effort to develop employees, employees will work for the well being of organisation and for human being also.

Free expression of Feelings:

Whatever Top management feels about employees they have to express to employees and whatever employees think about top management it must be express in other words we can say that there should not be anything hidden while communication process. Clear communication process will help to establish the HRD Climate.

Feedback:

Feedback should be taken regularly to know the drawbacks in system. This will help to gain confidence in employees mind. Employee will trust on management and he can express his opinion freely which is very good for HRD Climate. Feedback will help to remove the weakness.

Helpful nature of employee's:

Whenever we talk about 100% effort then we have to talk about employee's effort too. Nature of employee's should be helping for management and for its colleagues. They should be always read to help to customers too.

Supportive personnel management:

Personnel policies of organisation should motivate employees to contribute more from their part. Top management's philosophy should be clear towards Human Resource and its well being to encourage the employees.

Encouraging and risk taking experimentation:

Employee's should be motivated by giving them authority to take decision. This concept is risky but gradually it will bring expertise in employee's to handle similar situation in future. It will help to develop confidence in employees mind. Organization can utilize and develop employees more by assigning risky task.

Discouraging stereotypes and favouritism:

Management need to avoid those practices which lead to favoritism. Management and Managers need to give equal importance. Those people who are performing good they need to appreciate and those who are not performing well they need to be guided. Any kind of partial behaviour should be avoided.

Team Spirit:

There must be feeling of belongingness among the employees, and also willingness to work as a team.

Human resource development in the organizational context is a process by which the employees of an organization are helped in a continuous, planned way to: (a) acquire or sharpen capabilities required to perform various functions associated with their present or expected future roles; (b) develop their general capabilities as individuals and discover and exploit their own inner potentials for their own and/or organizational development processes; and (c) develop an organizational culture in which supervisor-subordinate relationships, team work and collaboration among sub units are strong and contribute to the professional well-being, motivation and pride of employees. The positive HRD climate renders the existing systems more effective and makes the organizations more receptive to the introduction of relevant additional system. Organizations differ in the extent to which they have these tendencies. Some organizations may have some of these tendencies, some others may have only a few of these and a few may have most of these.

OBJECTIVES

The study has been undertaken to:

- To analyze the work culture and HRD Climate prevailing in Cadbury India Ltd.
- To study the HRD climate considering Prospect, work culture, professionalism and Training & development as parameters
- To study variances among four parameters affecting work culture and HRD climate

HYPOTHESIS

In view of the objectives set for the study the following null and alternative hypothesis has been

Formulated respectively:

H₀ : There exists no significant variances among all four parameters and its responses given by employees of Cadbury India Ltd.

H₁ : There exists significant variances among all four parameters and its responses given by employees of Cadbury India Ltd.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive approach has been used to find out work culture and HRD climate from 50 employees working at administrative department. Primary data has been collected using structured questionnaire consist of total 27 questions using 3 point likert scale. Questionnaire consist of 4 questions for Prospect, 10 questions for work culture, 8 questions for professionalism, 5 questions for training & development. Samples are selected using convenience sampling (non-probability). Single factor ANOVA has been performed using Excel sheet to find out variances among all four parameters and its responses given by employees .

DATA COLLECTION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table : 1 Summated score of 27 questions for all four parameters.

	Agree	Somewhat agree	Disagree
Prospect	360	84	38
Work Culture	690	374	83
Professionalism	666	218	69
Training & development	540	86	27

(Source : Compiled from questionnaire)

Table : 2 Data Analysis

Anova: Single Factor

SUMMARY

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Prospect	3	482	160.6667	30329.33
Work Culture	3	1147	382.3333	92164.33
Professionalism	3	953	317.6667	96552.33
Training & development	3	653	217.6667	78794.33

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	88748.25	3	29582.75	0.397297	0.758698	4.066181
Within Groups	595680.7	8	74460.08			

Total 684428.9 11

(Source : Compiled from questionnaire)

Result of ANOVA : Calculated value 0.397

Critical value 4.07

As calculated value is less than critical value H0 is rejected which means there is significant variance among all four parameters.

Refer for detail Annexure:2

FINDINGS

- There is a significant variance among four parameters such as prospect, work culture, professionalism & training & development as critical value (4.07) is greater than calculated value (0.397).
- 75% of the employees selected are agreed about prospect HRD climate.
- 60% of the employees selected are positive about work culture of the organization.

- 70% of the employees selected have an opinion that company adopts professionalism in its culture.
- 83% of the employees selected are positive about training & developmental activities at the organization.

CONCLUSION

- HRD climate needs to be improved at Cadbury India Ltd. An organization work culture seems to be moderate while the more professional approach needs to be developing to create skill and competent employees. There is significant variance among all four parameters considered to describe HRD climate in the organization.

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